
Comparitive Study of Kolkata's ITES Employee Needs: Females Vs Males

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ABSTRACT

Large scale attrition in an organisation in the current competitive market may be detrimental to its image and business continuity. To avoid such undesired situations, organisational planners often introduce retention policies. The effectiveness of such policies depends on how much such interventions fulfill the needs and aspirations of the contemporary workforce. The needs harbored by the pool of employees of the ITES sector are not uniform across the genders. Through my research, I have tried to capture such unique employee needs that the latter expects to be fulfilled by their employers. Through the use of inferential statistical tools, I have identified the in-demand needs of both the groups of employees segregated basis their genders (*male and female employee pool*). In my research the identified employee needs were further ranked basis the intensity of demand. A comparative analysis was also done to highlight the similarities and differences that exists among such needs of both the groups of employees who are working in the ITES sector of Kolkata. Such knowledge will be helpful for any organisational policy framer for developing more effective and thus better retention strategies.

Introduction

India ranks first in the world when it comes to population size as well as the rate of growth of GDP, when compared to large economies of the world. On many an occasion the importance of the demographic dividend of India and the impact of the same has been emphasised by the leaders of the nations around the world. The total population of India is almost equally divided amongst the members of both the genders – females and males. When it comes to the distribution of the two genders exclusively amongst the population of India that is working in the organized sector, the percentage of woman, as per report of the Directorate of General Employment stands at 42%. A large portion of these employees are employed by organisations belonging to the ITES sector of India. According to reports published in Business Standard (2025), the percentage of female employees joining in the sector is about 28%. According to Ernst & Young (EY), by 2030, India will have the highest percentage of Working Age Population at 68.9% and according to Statista, woman will contribute to about 48% of the total population of India by 2030.

The ITES sector recently has been in news because of high rates of attrition amongst its employees. As a result of such attritions, organisations and in-turn nations face outflow of knowledge (brain drain) that is very difficult to replace. Attrition is an economic trouble for an employer. The cost incurred by an employer in training onboarding and nurturing a talent is lost, whenever a talent walks out. To prevent the same, employers come with retention policies but without understanding what an employee expects from the employer (employee needs) the retention initiatives often fail to deliver desired results.

In my research, I have tried to investigate and understand what expectations are harbored by the male and female employees of the ITES sector from their employers. I have focused on the vibrant ITES sector of the Kolkata for my research where I have presented a comparative analysis of the needs of the concerned employees.

Review of Literature

During my research endeavor, I studied multiple publications to understand the employee needs of the contemporary ITES sector in India. I have studied separately articles that highlights several challenges that are faced by female as well as male employees of the sector in general. I have also studied multiple literature regarding the various needs of employee in general who are working in this sector across India.

In Table:1, I have highlighted some of the critical challenges that has been identified to be experienced by the female employees of this sector in general, along with the details of the sources of the studies which proposed the same.

Table:1 Challenges faced by Female ITES employees

Challenge	Author/Source
Career stagnation, Lack of Flexible Work Policy, Gender bias/ stereotypes, Limited learning opportunities	Larissa Soares et al. (2023); Communications Today Editorial (2024); Shondell Williams et al. (2025)
Excessive Stress	Larissa Soares et al. (2023)
Barriers to entry	Ewa Makowska-Flumak et al. (2025); Shondell Williams et al. (2025)
Pay disparity, Limited leadership representation	Communications Today Editorial (2024); Business Standard Research Desk (2025)

In Table:2, I have highlighted some of the critical challenges that has been identified to be experienced by the employees in this sector in general, along with the details of the sources of the studies which proposed the same.

Table:2 Common challenges faced by ITES employe

Challenge	Author/Source
Job Insecurity, Heavy Perceived Workload, Shift Timings, Performance Targets, Work-Life Imbalance	Chandawad, M.M. & Suryawanshi, S.M. (2025) Deshpande, R. & Chakraborty, D. (2023)
Power Politics, Dissatisfaction with colleagues, Lack of recognition, Monotonous nature of the job	Mishra (2018)
Mismatch of Employee skills and assigned job	Thite, Mohan & Russell, Bob (2010)

Employees who experience such challenges, over time grows desire to overcome them and it is this desire that slowly transforms into a need that if not fulfilled by the employer, drives the employee to attrite from that particular organisation.

In my research, I have tried to identify and analyses and compare such needs of male and female ITES employees of Kolkata which if not satisfied may push them to attrite from their current organisations.

Research Methodology

The research was conducted in the second and third quarter of FY'25 in the city of Kolkata. The primary raw data for the research was collected by deploying a structured questionnaire containing forty-two open-ended questions.

A total of 360 ITES employees took part in the survey for my research; out of which 181 were males and 179 were females. The adequacy of this sample was tested through KMO (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin) test.

Inferential statistical tools like principal component factor analysis were used to identify the major need clusters that are in demand amongst the surveyed employee pool. The significance of correlation between the variables was analysed using the *Bartlett's Test of sphericity*.

ANOVA was also deployed to understand the significance of the relation between the need clusters and their respective impact on the employee's intent to attrite.

SPSS (26.0) was utilized to conduct the various statistical analysis.

Data Analysis

Table: 3 shows the factors that were in demand among the female ITES employees, that if not provided may lead to their eventual voluntary attrition; identified through principal component factor analysis.

Table: 3 – Needs of Female ITES Employees

FACTOR COUNT	FACTOR	CONTRIBUTION
1	Compensation	4.968 of 17.133%
2	Work – Life Balance with Clarity	3.707 of 12.782%
3	Affordable Employee Healthcare Plans	3.111 of 10.729%
4	Safe and Reliable Employee Transportation	3.003 of 10.354%
5	Job Security	2.990 of 10.312%
6	Approachable and Supportive Leadership	2.962 of 10.213%
7	Employee Empowerment	2.936 of 10.124%
8	Career Growth and Internal Mobility	1.934 of 6.667%

The KMO value for this PCA was at .817 with a significance of .000.

Table: 4 shows the factors that were in demand among the male ITES employees, that if not provided may lead to their eventual voluntary attrition; identified through principal component factor analysis.

Table: 4 – Needs of Male ITES Employees

FACTOR COUNT	FACTOR	CONTRIBUTION
1	Compensation	5.403 of 18.011%
2	Work – Life Balance with Clarity	4.884 of 16.281%
3	Personal Wellbeing	4.055 of 13.518%
4	Approachable and Supportive Leadership	3.226 of 10.755%
5	Importance at Workplace	2.922 of 9.740%
6	Career Growth and Internal Mobility	2.921 of 9.735%

The KMO value for this PCA was at .879 with a significance of .000.

To understand whether each of the factors have significant impact on the intention to attrite amongst the respective groups of responders ANOVA was performed.

Table: 5 till table Table:12 captures the ANOVA results comparing the identified needs and the dependent variable '*Intent to Attrite*' amongst the *Female employees* surveyed during my research.

Table: 5 – ANOVA (Compensation vs Intent to Attrite)

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	39.348	8	4.918	6.566	.000
Within Groups	125.101	167	.749		
Total	164.449	175			

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	53.347	17	3.138	4.463	.000
Within Groups	111.102	158	.703		
Total	164.449	175			

Table: 6 – ANOVA (Work Life Balance with Clarity vs Intent to Attrite)

Table: 7- ANOVA (Affordable Employee Healthcare Plans vs Intent to Attrite)

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	37.528	9	4.170	5.454	.000
Within Groups	126.921	166	.765		
Total	164.449	175			

Table: 8 - ANOVA (Safe and Reliable Employee Transportation vs Intent to Attrite)

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	16.415	7	2.345	2.661	.000
Within Groups	148.033	168	.881		
Total	164.449	175			

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	28.215	7	4.031	4.971	.000
Within Groups	136.234	168	.811		
Total	164.449	175			

Table: 9 - ANOVA (Job Security vs Intent to Attrite)

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	39.625	11	3.602	4.733	.000
Within Groups	124.823	164	.761		
Total	164.449	175			

Table: 10 - ANOVA (Approachable and Supportive Leadership vs Intent to Attrite)

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	47.015	21	1.921	2.384	.000
Within Groups	117.434	165	.712		
Total	164.449	175			

Table: 11 - ANOVA (Employee Empowerment and Flexibility vs Intent to Attrite)

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	40.349	21	1.921	2.384	.001
Within Groups	124.100	154	.806		
Total	164.449	175			

Table: 12 - ANOVA (Career Growth and Internal Mobility vs Intent to Attrite)

Table: 13 till Table:18 captures the ANOVA results comparing the identified needs and the dependent variable '*Intent to Attrite*' amongst the *Male employees* surveyed during my research.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	75.160	11	6.833	7.561	0.000
Within Groups	221.399	245	0.904		
Total	296.558	256			

Table: 13 - ANOVA (Compensation vs Intent to Attrite)

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	74.058	18	4.114	4.401	0.000
Within Groups	222.500	238	0.935		
Total	296.558	256			

Table: 14 - ANOVA (Work – Life Balance with Clarity vs Intent to Attrite)

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	63.543	24	2.648	2.636	0.000
Within Groups	233.016	232	1.004		
Total	296.558	256			

Table: 15 - ANOVA (Personal Wellbeing vs Intent to Attrite)

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	31.771	10	3.177	2.952	0.002
Within Groups	264.787	246	1.076		

Total	296.558	256			
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Table: 16 - ANOVA (Approachable and Supportive Leadership vs Intent to Attrite)

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	63.067	19	3.319	3.369	0.000
Within Groups	233.491	237	0.985		
Total	296.558	256			

Table: 17 - ANOVA (Importance at Workplace vs Intent to Attrite)

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	74.058	18	4.114	4.401	0.000
Within Groups	222.500	238	0.935		
Total	296.558	256			

Table: 18 - ANOVA (Career Growth and Internal Mobility vs Intent to Attrite)

Data Interpretation & Recommendation

Post observing the ANOVA results in Tables 5-18, it can be stated that each of the factors have significant contribution upon the intent to attrite amongst the respective employee pool.

When it comes to the principal factors that impacts attrition intents amongst the two pools of concerned employees, it is evident that compensation has the highest impact. This finding has underlined the fact that the organisations need to urgently reconfigure their pay structures and must ensure that the salaries that they are offering are in line with the contemporary markets. The significance associated with compensation by male employees is much higher compared to the others, which is an indication of the fact that they have a higher chance of attrition compared to females if such needs are ignored.

Comparing Factor 2 from both Tables 3 and 4, it is evident that there is a desire from both sets of employees to be part of such organisations when the leadership is competent enough to give clarity of not just work assigned to an employee. Alongside that, employees also desire a leadership that will be good enough to ensure that the distribution of tasks(work) is done in such a manner that individual employees could strike a balance between their personal and professional commitments.

Factor 3 in Table:4 is an outcome of the impacts of two sets of facilities that male employees expect from their employers in tandem. For them, personal wellbeing can only be ensured if they get covered by employer provided health insurance as well as they receive safe and reliable transportation facilities. On the contrary, for female employees, both these facilities do not hold shared importance. When it comes to preference, an employer health insurance policy is a higher need for a female employee than transportation facilities. This is evident from the relative impacts of Factors 3 and 4 in Table:3.

Factor 5 in Table:3 is interesting, since the same does not find significance for the male employees of the sector in Kolkata. This is an indication that the males are more open to change compared to female employees and are OK to be part of any institute with low job security if the latter fulfills other expectations.

What ranks as the fifth most important need for males is in the sixth position for females. Both employee types prefer their leadership to be accessible and extend necessary support when required.

Factor 7 in Table:3 indicates the fact that female employees' desires to be empowered in the workplace. This data reflects that till date in many organisations, the female employees are often not trusted with authority. Such treatment often pushes such employees to look for alternate employers who are willing to provide them the same.

Factor 5 in Table:4 highlights the need for a male employee to be given importance at workplace. If any male employee is ignored or is not given due recognition for his efforts, then the chances of such employee attrition will be high.

Lastly, Factors 6 and 8 of Tables: 3 and 4 respectively capture the importance of employers preparing and deploying appropriate organisational policies that will ensure that employees get the chance to progress their professional careers by properly utilizing their talents and skills within the organisations, by fluid inter-team movements and by doing so be more productive and achieve career progression. Failing to implement such initiatives and processes, will leave an employer vulnerable to attrition of skilled talent as is evident from the significance associated with this need by both the groups of employees surveyed.

Conclusion

India is a growing economy, and the rate of growth can only be sustained by ensuring proper integration of male and female talent pools. Loss of talent by attrition is a significant challenge for any employer.

Attrition, if high, may jeopardies the viability of running of any business. Employers must understand the needs and expectations of their contemporary employees. Such knowledge is the key to develop a solid retention intervention. Through my research, any policy maker, especially those in the ITES sector, can better develop their retention initiatives for those employees who are working in the city of Joy, Kolkata.

References

- Chandawad, M.M. & Suryawanshi, S.M. (2025). Workplace Stress and Its Effects on Productivity: An Empirical Study of BPO Employees. Retrieved from: <https://www.iarj.in/index.php/ijracm/article/view/401>
- Deshpande, R. & Chakraborty, D. (2023). Impact of Work Stressors on Career Commitment A Study of Indian IT Sector Employees <https://doi.org/10.17010/pijom/2023/v16i11/173214>
- Ministry of Labour and Employment. (2023). Female Labour Utilization in India. Retrieved from: https://dge.gov.in/dge/sites/default/files/2023-05/Female_Labour_Utilization_in_India_April_2023_final__1_-_pages-1-2-merged__1_.pdf
- Ministry of Statistics & Programme Implementation, Government of India. (2022). WOMEN AND MEN IN INDIA 2022. Retrieved from: https://www.mospi.gov.in/sites/default/files/publication_reports/women-men22/WomenMen2022.pdf
- Mishra. P. & Solanki, N. (2018). A study of the factors leading to attrition in employees of BPO Industry with special focus on attitude towards job and employee engagement: 2018 IJCRT | Volume 6, Issue 2 April 2018 | ISSN: 2320-2882
- Thite, M., & Russell, B. (2010). Work Organization, human resource practices and employee retention in Indian Call Centers. *Asia Pacific Journal of Human Resources*. 48(3), 356-374
- Women in Services Sector CII. (2025). Participation of Indian women in workforce rises from 23% to 42% in six years. Retrieved from: <https://ddnews.gov.in/en/participation-of-indian-women-in-workforce-rises-from-23-to-42-in-six-years/>

- World Bank. (2024). Population, female – India. Retrieved from:
<https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SP.POP.TOTL.FE.IN?locations=IN>